

IDENTIFICATION CATALOGUE

**MACROBENTHIC FAUNA OF
ORMONDE SEAMOUNT**

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The **MEDWAVES** (MEDiterranean out flow Water and Vulnerable EcosystemS) cruise targeted areas under the potential influence of the MOW within the Mediterranean and Atlantic realms. These include seamounts where Cold-water corals (CWCs) have been reported but that are still poorly known, and which may act as essential “stepping stones” connecting fauna of seamounts in the Mediterranean with those of the continental shelf of Portugal, the Azores and the Mid-Atlantic Ridge.

One of this target areas is the **Ormonde seamount**; where four ROV videos transects (D) were conducted between 660 and 1960 m depth to explore the deep-sea macrobenthic communities.

Panel 1– PHYLUM PORIFERA

(a) *Phakellia ventilabrum*, (b) *Petrosia* cf. *crassa*, (c) *Petrosia* sp. 1, (d) *Petrosia* sp. 2, (e) *Petrosia* sp. 3, (f) *Hymedesmia curvichela*, (g) *Polymastia* sp., (h) *Stylocordyla* cf. *pellita*, (i) *Leiodermatium pfeifferae*, (j) *Corallistes* sp., (k) *Neophrissospongia nolitangere*, (l) *Geodia* cf. *atlántica*, (m) *Geodia* cf. *barretti*, (n) *Geodia* sp., (o) *Macandrewia azorica*.

Panel 2 – PHYLUM PORIFERA

(a) *Characella pachastrelloides* and *Hexadella dedritifera*, (b) *Hyalonema* cf. (*Cyliconema*) *thomsonis*, (c) *Hyalonema* cf. (*Cyliconema*) *infundibulum*, (d) *Pheronema carpenteri*, (e) *Regadrella Phoenix*, (f) *Asconema setubalense*, (g) *Sympagella* sp., (h) *Aphrocallistes beatrix*, (i) *Farrea occa*, (j) *Porifera digitate*, (k) *Porifera* sp.1, (l) *Porifera* sp.2, (m) *Porifera fistulose*, (n) *Porifera* sp.4, (o) *Porifera* sp.5.

Panel 3 – **PHYLA PORIFERA (a-c) AND CNIDARIA (d-o)**

(a) Porifera sp.6, (b) Porifera sp.7, (c) Porifera sp.8, (d) cf. *Actinoscyphia* sp., (e) Cnidaria sp., (f) *Acanthogorgia* sp., (g) *Iridogorgia* sp., (h) *Metallogorgia* sp., (i) *Radicipes* sp., (j) cf. *Viminella* sp., (k) *Acanella arbuscula*, (l) Plexauridae sp.1, (m) Plexauridae sp.2, (n) *Swiftia* sp., (o) *Narella bellissima*.

Panel 4 – PHYLUM CNIDARIA

(a) *Narella versluyisi*, (b) Alcyonacea sp.1, (c) Alcyonacea sp.2, (d) Alcyonacea sp.3, (e) cf. *Leiopathes* sp., (f) *Bathypathes* sp., (g) *Parantipathes* sp., (h) *Stichopathes* cf. *gravieri*, (i) *Stichopathes* sp., (j) *Corallimorphus* sp., (k) cf. *Protoptilidae* sp., (l) *Lophelia pertusa*, (m) *Caryophylliidae* sp., (n) *Enallopsammia rostrata*, (o) *Epizoanthus* sp.

Panel 5 - **PHYLA CNIDARIA (a-f) AND ECHINODERMATA (g-o)**

(a) Ceriantharia sp.1, (b) Ceriantharia sp.2, (c) cf. *Diphasia* sp., (d) Hydrozoa sp.1, (e) Hydrozoa sp.2, (f) Hydrozoa sp.3, (g) Goniasteridae sp.1, (h) Goniasteridae sp.2, (i) Asteroidea sp.1, (j) Asteroidea sp.2, (k) Asteroidea sp.3, (l) Asteroidea sp.4, (m) cf. *Leptometra* sp., (n) Crinoidea sp.1, (o) Crinoidea sp.2.

Panel 6 – **PHYLA ECHINODERMATA (a-i) AND CHORDATA (fish; j-o)**

(a) Crinoidea sp.3, (b) cf. Hyocrinida sp., (c) *Echinus* sp., (d) *Cidaris* sp., (e) Echinoidea sp.1, (f) Holothuroidea sp., (g) Ophiuroidea sp.1, (h) Ophiuroidea sp.2, (i) Ophiuroidea sp.3, (j) *Bathysaurus* sp., (k) *Hoplostethus* sp.1, (l) *Hoplostethus* sp.2, (m) Macrouridae sp.1, (n) Macrouridae sp.2, (o) *Mora moro*.

Panel 7 – **PHYLA CHORDATA** (fish; a-k) **AND ARTHROPODA** (Crustacea; l-o)

(a) Actinopterygii sp.7, (b) Actinopterygii sp.8, (c) Actinopterygii sp.9, (d) Actinopterygii sp.1, (e) Actinopterygii sp.2, (f) Actinopterygii sp.3, (g) Actinopterygii sp.4, (h) Actinopterygii sp.5, (i) Actinopterygii sp.6, (j) cf. *Deania* sp., (k) *Oxynotus* sp., (l) *Aristaeopsis edwardsiana*, (m) cf. *Chaceon affinis*, (n) *Paromola* sp., (o) *Munididae* spp.

Panel 8 – **PHYLA ARTHROPODA** (Crustacea; a-e and Pycnogonida; f), **MOLLUSCA** (Cephalopoda; g), **ANNELIDA** (Polychaeta; h) and unidentified organisms (i-j)

(a) Paguroidea sp., (b) Brachyura sp.2, (c) Decapoda sp.1, (d) Decapoda sp.2, (e) Decapoda sp.3, (f) cf. Pycnogonida sp., (g) Squid, (h) Polychaeta sp., (i) Undefined sp., (j) Unkown sp.

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